

Igbo Women's Emancipation in Flora Nwapa's *Women Are Different*

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ABSTRACT: The present study casts light on Igbo women's emancipation in Flora Nwapa's *Women Are Different*. In this respect, our purpose is to show how Nwapa suggests a narration based on Igbo women's emancipation in her *Women Are Different*. As such, the matter in this study lies on the realities experienced by Igbo women that Flora Nwapa resorts to portray the emancipation in her novel. In the same token, how does Nwapa define the Igbo women's emancipation in *Women are Different*? For the achievement of this study, we resort to sociological, psychological and feminist approaches. As results, Flora Nwapa resorts to various stories and social situations related to Igbo women to define their emancipation. Furthermore, Nwapa purposely resorts to the stories of education, travel and success in life of Igbo women's life experience to illustrate her concern on the portrayal of Igbo women's emancipation. As a matter of fact, Flora Nwapa's novel, *Women Are Different* remains a fight for the Igbo young girls' emancipation.

KEYWORDS: Igbo-Women, Emancipation, Education, Travel, Success

INTRODUCTION

When writing novels, African writers resort to various realities and social situations related to their social background to share their experience. This can be noticed in Flora Nwapa's novel, *Women Are Different*. In this respect, our study is about Igbo Women's Emancipation in Flora Nwapa's "*wWomen Are Different*." As far as the review of literature is concerned, many critics have studied Flora Nwapa's *Women Are Different*. In his doctoral dissertation, Mears (2009) analyzes women and culture in Flora Nwapa's fiction. Titem Nadi (2020) studied the representation of Nigerian Women in Flora Nwapa's *Efuru* and Chimamanda Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*. In his article, Amouzou (2006) showed how Flora Nwapa's fiction contributes to a redefinition of the female gender and a counter identification. Nème Diakite (2022) studied the dilemma of African women in Flora Nwapa's and Buchi Emecheta's novels. Finally, Fatma Kalpakli (2017) wrote on the Women Issue in Flora Nwapa's *Women Are Different*. It sorts out from these studies that Flora Nwapa stands against the traditional legacy of Igbo women, their victimization by denouncing abuses of all sort.

As far as the organization of the study is concerned, it is made of three main sections. In section one, we focus on exposure to modern education. In section two, we concentrate on the issue of travelling in Nwapa's writing. At last, we devote our attention on insight into job and success in Rose's life.

1. An Exposure to Modern Education

This section offers an analysis of an exposure to modern and Western's education by Nigerian women in general and Igbo women in particular by Flora Nwapa in *Women Are Different*. Nwapa presents Igbo girls' modern education as synonym of emancipation for Nigerian females in general and Igbo females in particular. In fact, the *Concise Oxford English Dictionary* defines education as "a process of teaching, training and learning, especially in schools or colleges, to improve knowledge and develop skills."

A long time ago, African continent faces many problems disturbing its growth and preventing it from standing up towards its emergence. Among those problems, we can quote education. Indeed, being the most likely way for the development, education becomes the business of African writers as we can mention among them Flora Nwapa who focuses on the theme of education in Nigeria. Illustrated by different instances in *Women Are Different*, the matter of education is highly supported by Flora Nwapa. The first chapter of Nwapa's novel makes it the main issue. As a matter of fact, Nwapa opens her novel with the situation of modern education through the competitive entrance examination of some girls. This is evidenced when Nwapa (1992, p.1) writes:

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They came to school on the same day, having passed the competitive entrance examination to enter the first secondary school for girls set up by the Anglican Mission in Nigeria. Hitherto there was Denis Gemorial Grammar School; Orika Grammar School, and far away in Efik land, Hope Waddel.

It is clear that these girls come to school to a test for their school education, that is why they should pass their competitive entrance examination to enter the first secondary school for girls. This above quotation betrays the fact that, in the colonial period in Africa, by the lack of means and knowledge, African schools were ruled by settlers in mission to educate black people. It is revealed that, the competitive entrance examination to enter the first secondary school takes place in Port Harcourt: "they sat for the examination in Port Harcourt, and all three of them sat side by side. They do not actually spy on one another, but they are all disposed to each other" (1992, p.1). For the test, all the girls have to be concentrated and deal with subjects such as: arithmetic and English. This can be noticed in the following Nwapa's (1992, p.1) words:

After the first paper which was arithmetic, (...) Then Dora said that as a matter of fact, they were all going to the examination with full marks (...) Look, forget arithmetic and think of English which we will go in for in a few minutes(...) The bell rang. It was time for the English paper and the three girls walked to the examination hall.

Additionally, the white woman has been responsible for the distribution of all the examination papers not only for the three girls but for all about a hundred girls in the hall. The remarkable fact is that, the white woman is already very familiar with the spoken pidgin English used in the Port Harcourt space but, she does not use it in the school. She also does not allow girls to speak the pidgin in the school. In this connection, Flora Nwapa (1992, p.2) asserts:

The white woman could not hide her amusement. She was already used to pidgin English spoken in the Port Harcourt area. And in the school there was a rule that forbade girls from speaking pidgin English. (...) She distributed the examination papers to girls. There were about a hundred girls in the hall, and in a short time, she had given them all papers, and then asked them to read the instructions very carefully before answering the questions. When she made sure they now understood her, she asked them to start. It is revealed that the white woman manages to speak slowly only in English to be understood by the girls. To avoid any type of misunderstanding, she should have taken one of her Nigerian teachers to her side all along the examination time till its end. Thanks to her pedagogical senses, she tries many times to speak more slowly to make herself understood by the girls. She emphasizes on the reading of instructions first, before doing any other things.

Provided by westerners to Nigerian children, education is not easy to be caught by Nigerian learners because of the language use. So, the way the girls used to speak at home is very different from the way teachers use at school, though the both speak the same language. This fact is presented by the author in the novel, where it is said: "when she spoke, Rose did not understand a word of what she said" (Nwapa, 1992, p.2)

One can understand that, it is not easy to be educated if the knowledge is transmitted through a language you do not often use. Accordingly, the girls could say: "We can hear you, but we cannot understand you" (Nwapa, 1992, p.2). They receive two kinds of education like scholar education and religious one. These educational accounts show how women were educated at school and in church. So, it is clear that they receive a good education at school, because in the novel Nwapa describes the Nigerian women who pass their certificate examination. Also, Christianity has been taught to them as it is mentioned: "Christian teachings". Both educations are like a gift which helps them to live in the society (Nwapa, 1992, p.40). Admittedly, Agnes, Dora and Rose, the three determined Igbo girls break the Igbo traditional system of education to stand for the Western one through their success as it can be read in the following Nwapa's (1992, p.3) words:

Time was up and the answer papers were collected by the small white woman (...). They had all passed the entrance examination to Archdeacon Crowther Memorial Girls' School (ACMGS) Elelewa, and they were now going to the school to start their first year. This extract from the novel shows that the new girls feel better. Agnes, Dora and Rose sit together. The results of this analysis reveal that, in the few days that followed they adjust to the routine of the school, and discover that though it is hard, especially getting up at five thirty in the morning to fetch water half a mile away; doing house work, and cooking the meals, they enjoy: "their classes, their games, and reading" (Nwapa, 1992, p.10). In this connection, girls are now exposed to the new world of books. Stories fascinate them, and they read everything they could lay their hands on: "One of the older girls smuggled in the magazine to the school, and girls read them to their hearts' content. Agnes, Rose and Dora shared books" (Nwapa, 1992, p.10).

We can also point out some of secondary themes. Concerning Flora Nwapa's novel, *Women Are Different*, we have realized that education is the main theme in the chapter one, but some secondary themes are also noticeable. Indeed, in the same chapter we can underline the theme of friendship developed by the author. So, the friendship stands as one of the subsidiary themes of the first chapter performed by the three girls named: Rose, Dora, and Agnes, Nigerian natives. Through, the novel, the author shows us how the girls became friends. During the examination, they were concerned at the first paper, Rose did not work well, it was Arithmetic paper, just after the exam "Rose wept uncontrollably." Agnes and Dora felt touched, they "(...) sympathized with her." The theme of friendship is also supported in the fact that three girls used to talk as a unit by a motivation "Dora said that (...), they were all going to pass the examination with full marks" (Nwapa, 1992, p.1). They believed in their relationship something endless that will separate them across time. Reason why the author said: "they would be admitted to the school in January of 1945 and that they would all be in the same dormitory." (Nwapa, 1992, p.1)

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Coming from different schools, the three girls have created a great friendship during the examination which gather them some hours later. After the exam, they were supposed to return back to their different schools. So, to preserve the union, they: "(...) exchanged addresses and went back to their different schools." (Nwapa, 1992, p.3). Always under the theme of friendship, the author reserved us a great surprise with the meeting of the three at the railway station in January 1945. It is clear that they all passed the entrance examination. The three girls were happy to discuss again. In short, in *Women Are Different*, Flora Nwapa describes the Nigerian women's system of education. This resulted to the conclusion that the Nigerian women received both school education and church education which was based on Christianity. So, school education allowed those women to pass entrance examination in renowned schools such as Archdeacon Growther Memorial Girls' School (AGMGS).

2. Travel

Travel is noticed in *Women Are Different* through three main places: Nigeria, England and the United States of America. It plays an important role in the girls' emancipation. In fact, people can talk about journeys when Rose flies to the University of London for getting a diploma and return back to Nigeria as Nwapa (1992, p.79) says:

At Queen's College Lagos, Rose attempted the entrance to the University College, Ibadan and failed. She returned home to Aba, taught in a girl's school (...). She was admitted into Ibadan in 1953, and missed Ernest who had left Ibadan and gone abroad to continue his medical studies. She graduated and went to the university of London for her Diploma in education. She returned to Nigeria and was appointed as a Woman Education Officer in Queen's College...

Rose is sent abroad again for her training concerning the new job. With the help of Mark, "Rose gets her passport, withdrew all her savings and gives it to Mark. She is to follow him as soon as she is admitted into Harvard." (Nwapa, 1992, p.82). Mark writes a week after his arrival in the States, and said he would write again as soon he settled down, and had an address. But weeks, months passed and Rose did not hear from Mark. She is not acquainted as such with Mark's friends. So, she could not ask them about Mark. It is revealed that Rose takes a leave of absence and visits Aba where Mark said his parents are, but his parents are not there. She comes back to Lagos. Slowly it begins to dawn on her that Mark has jilted her. She has lost contact with Ernest, now Mark. She becomes miserable, feels sorry for herself and weeps, but doesn't share her sorrow with someone. She goes about her business with great effort but she controls her emotions as Flora Nwapa (1992, p.83) writes:

Thank God she was not pregnant. But couldn't it have been better if she were pregnant? After all, her friends in ACMGS were married and had children. If she were pregnant, she would have had something to look forward to, a baby, boy or girl it did not matter. Nearly eight years after leaving school, she could only boast of a degree and nothing else. But she consoled herself. Mark was not the end of the world.

To forget and look forward to the future, Rose decides to leave Queen's and looks for another job in Lagos. Of course, where else? So, in 1959 she gets a job with a firm of public relations.

In other terms, the travel is classified as one of the key elements of emancipation in *Women Are Different*. The travel regards girls as learners having passed their entrance examination, left their location to continue their studies in other localities. They travel by train, that is the case of Rose, Agnes, Dora and other girls coming from Aba and its surroundings as we can read: "The girls crossed the railway line quickly and made their way to the school, while the train, this time coming from Aba, was bringing the girls resident in Aba and its environ to AGMGS" (Nwapa, 1992, p.6).

Aba girls are not the last to join school at Elenwa. There are also those coming from ENUGU. Their train arrives when the girls are playing and running to the railway station to welcome the others, among them Rose's cousin. So, the travel in *Women Are Different* is not only made by train. Indeed, girls should join boys to ACMGS. According to Flora Nwapa (1992, pp.13-14):

But two days to the day, the kit car which was to drive the boys to ACMGS developed engine trouble. Miss Hill was so upset. She had had so much trouble over the debate, and whatever was in her power to do, she would do to please the girls. There was a staff meeting and there it was decided that the girls could go to Okrika by canoe (...). Comfort could not swim but she said she would go all the same; the canoe was not going to capsize.

There is a debate about travelling by canoe or not. Some boys and girls do not know how to swim. They are afraid of travelling by canoe because they are afraid of water. In the group, Rose, Dora and Agnes are all able to swim. Thus, they are confident to help others in the case of any difficulty: "Thank God! Rose could swim (...). Agnes and Dora are all swimmers, assured the others that if anything happened, they knew how to save them from drowning" (1992, p.14).

Nwapa illustrates the fact that travelling through water is also a risk, but it happens without any problem and the debate takes place. Always in the context of the travel, the girls who come for the debate, would be back to their school, but it is already night. The only means of transport available is walking. The travel here is characterized by the walk of girls who turn back to their own school. Talking about the travel is the fact of moving in a short or long way from a given town to another, "the travel" is developed in Nwapa's novel with many examples: "Rose worked hard in eighteen months, she had become a high executive. She was sent abroad for training for only three weeks, and returned full of new ideas and vigour" (1992, p.82).

Another travel is also seen in Nwapa's writing with Agnes, Rose and Dora who were going to Enugu City. According to Nwapa (1992, p.4):

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It was then Agnes, Rose and Dora looked round to get a glimpse of their surroundings. The railway station was bare and poor. The train that brought them having proceeded on its long and slow journey to the coal city, Enugu, they became aware of their surroundings. There was just a single railway line, and the station master's office.

A close analysis of the travelling by train reveals that, all along the railway line; sugar canes are abundant. During the travelling by train, children come with their long sugar cane stems to the windows of the coaches when the train makes a given stop at the given station. Children beg the passengers to buy their sugar canes. When people buy them, children cut them in tiny lengths for the passengers:

But then the township girl who had spoken to them had already bought ten lengths of sugar cane, and the child she bought them from was busy cutting them into tiny lengths. Agnes could not resist the sugar cane so she went over" (1992, p.5).

Here, we can understand some travelling debates between Rose, Agnes and Dora on their way to school where they pass their entrance examination. In the same way, the travelling is also remarkable in Flora Nwapa's novel by the travel of Rose when a plane takes her from the international airport to London via Port Harcourt. After arriving there, she decides in these words: "no, I think I should go back home ..." (1992, p.132). Then, she takes a car with a man from London to Aba. According to Nwapa (1992, p.132): They arrived in Port Harcourt after midnight. A company car was waiting and the driver drove them to Aba. They will drop me first since you are going into town, then he will take the car to his home in the village for it is too late for him to go home otherwise.

In addition, there is Agnes who is proposed to receive a passport and a return ticket to London. We can also point out the travel of the couple, Theo and Elizabeth. We also notice the elements which show the travel in the following extract:

Chris finally returned from Germany, and Dora threw a big party for him, to welcome him home. She asked her friends and business associates to come and rejoice with her for her husband whom she thought would never come back had returned (Nwapa, 1992, p.130).

There is also the travelling by plane presented by Nwapa (1986, p.130) in her *Women Are Different* as follows: (Travelling by plane comes to confirm the Nigerian women's emancipation): "Rose bought her ticket for Port Harcourt and set out for the airport with a week-end suitcase" (Nwapa, 1992, p.130). Then, "She queued again, and eventually got her boarding pass. She waited for the flight at the lounge (Nwapa, 1992, p.131).

In brief, we can say that travelling is one of the significant themes in Nwapa's writing. Simply because, travelling is visible in this novel in the case of her characters such as Rose, Dora, Anges, etc. who have travelled from here and there in the novel. In conclusion, their travellings are linked to the aim of obtaining certificates and diplomas in abroad countries in order to come back and serve their country which is Nigeria.

3. Rose and her life

In this section we aim at analyzing Rose's life in Flora Nwapa's *Women Are Different*, especially how she succeeded to obtain a job and how her life started to change in different communities that she used to live. First of all, Rose's life begins with the entrance in Ibadan University College that is illustrated on:

She returned home to Aba, taught in a girl's school and attempted the entrance to Ibadan again and passed. She was admitted into Ibadan in 1953, and missed Ernest who had left Ibadan and gone abroad to continue his medical studies (Nwapa, 1992, p.79).

This shows how Rose's life started to change once she returned home to Aba after failing to the University College of Ibadan, because she was even employed in a girl's school as a teacher. What is significant here is that Rose was later on admitted into the University College of Ibadan. According to Flora Nwapa (1986, p.79):

Ibadan days passed quickly for Rose. She graduated and went to the University of London for her Diploma in Education. While in London she tried to find Ernest, but could not. She returned to Nigeria and was appointed as Woman Education Officer in Queen's College, where she taught maths.

This extract explains how things improved in Rose's life, because she graduated at the University College in Ibadan, then she traveled from Ibadan to London for educational reasons. After that, she travelled again from London to Nigeria where she obtained a job as a teacher of Mathematics at Queen's College, in Lagos. Later on, according to Flora Nwapa (1986, p.82): "Rose decided to leave Queen's and look for another job in Lagos. Of course, where else? So, in 1959 she got a job with a firm of public relations." For Rose "any time you wake up is your morning" (1992, p.83). We can say that Rose never stops learning in her career because she could only boast of degree and nothing else as it is written on:

Rose worked hard and eighteen months, she had become a high executive. She was sent abroad for training for only three weeks, and she returned full of new ideas and vigour. Independence was round the corner. Nigerians were being trained to take over from the British. Rose was lucky to be in a position where she would use her brain and talent, and so she used it well (Nwapa, 1992, p.82).

Then, she regrets the time she wasted in Queen's College. "But then as we say, any time you wake up is your morning." She was satisfied to work at the right time. Then, "She moved to Ikoyi, had a large office and a secretary. If that was not success, what then was success? She thought of her school, her lovely and caring teachers, and the Christian upbringing she had had" (Nwapa, 1992, p.83).

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Moreover, Rose's success is known in this job as it is written in "At last, Rose works in her own office" (1992, p.83). Rose was in her own office: "Rose's secretary opened the door quietly and left. Rose looked at Janet" (p.83). In matters of facts, Rose becomes now a boss, thanks to her office of secretary. To support this point, Nwapa (1986, p.85) puts:

Olu had come to do business in Rose's office. It was a matter which Tinu could have handled very well. But for one reason or the other, Tinu asked her boss to see Olu. He was in Rose's office for exactly thirty minutes. Tinu served him a special coffee reserved for VIPs. He drank it slowly while they discussed the problem. He asked for another cup, and commented that it was very good coffee.

This quotation shows how Rose was considered as a boss, especially in her office of secretary, because "one day Olu came to Rose's office and asked her whether she could afford two weeks holiday in London. She could as she was her own boss" (Nwapa, 1992, p.87). So, Rose was really a boss, having even her own car.

As for success in Rose's life, in this section, people can point out Rose's ambition toward her education. In fact, she keeps moving forward even though she fails after her first entrance to the Ibadan university college. She does not give up her studies but just keeps working harder until she gets success. Moreover, her aim is to have more knowledge or to be more graduated so that she can cope with any situation wherever she goes. That is why, she travels to London (England) to enhance her skills and become scholar, expecting to major at University as illustrated in the following sentence "she graduated and went to the University of London for her Diploma in education" (Nwapa, 1992, p. 79).

In short, in Nwapa's *Women Are Different*, Rose can be regarded as the image of Nigerian women who went to study in foreign countries and decided to return back home for serving their country. So, she succeeds to obtain a job in her country thanks to the education that she acquired abroad. This allows the other Nigerian women to follow Rose's example.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that the present study focuses on Igbo women's emancipation in Flora Nwapa's *Women Are Different*. In this respect, our purpose has been to show how Nwapa suggests a narration based on Igbo women's emancipation in her novel. In fact, the matter in this study lies on the realities of Igbo women as experience Flora Nwapa resorts to portray Igbo women's emancipation in *Women Are Different*. For the achievement of this study, we resort to sociological, psychological and feminist approaches. As results, Flora Nwapa resorts to various stories and social situations related to Igbo women to define their emancipation. Furthermore, Nwapa purposely resorts to the stories of education, travel and success in life of Igbo women's life experience to illustrate her concern on the portrayal of Igbo women's emancipation. In a word, Flora Nwapa's novel, *Women Are Different* remains a fight for the Igbo young girls' emancipation.

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